

Differential Expression of NOTCH1 gene in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma: Impact of Gender, HPV Status, and Tumour Stage"

Mohammad Reshma¹, Roy Anitha²

¹Department of Anatomy, Malla Reddy Medical College for Women, Hyderabad, Telangana.

²Department of Pharmacology, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.

Abstract:

Head and neck squamous cell carcinomas (HNSCC) constitute a heterogeneous group of cancers, which include cancers arising at the oral cavity, nasopharynx, oropharynx, hypopharynx, and larynx. This was a Prospective and observational studies in head and neck cancer patients Cohort – 60 cases of head and neck cancers (20 cases of Tongue; 20 cases of Epiglottis; 20 cases of hard palate) conducted at Malla Reddy Medical college and tertiary care hospitals in Hyderabad. Adults aged ≥ 18 years diagnosed with head and neck cancer (HNC). (C)RT patients discussed in a Head and Neck MDT meeting and deemed medically fit for an agreed treatment plan for primary or adjuvant radiotherapy \pm concurrent or induction chemotherapy (cisplatin or cetuximab). The NOTCH1 gene plays a role in cellular development and differentiation, and its expression can be altered in various cancers, including those associated. We have identified HNSCC cases with low Somatic copy number alterations (SCNAs) that differentiate as a subset of head and neck cancers driven predominantly by gene mutations and focal alterations rather than chromosomal instability events and are characterized by an improved overall survival.

Keywords: Genetic analysis, Mutant genes, Head and neck cancer, NOTCH1, HPV, Gender.

Introduction:

According to WHO Cancer is a large group of diseases that can start in almost any organ or tissue of the body when abnormal cells grow uncontrollably, go beyond their usual boundaries to invade adjoining parts of the body and/or spread to other organs. ^[1] Head and neck squamous cell carcinomas (HNSCC) constitute a heterogeneous group of cancers, which include cancers arising at the oral cavity, nasopharynx, oropharynx, hypopharynx, and larynx. ^[2]

Worldwide, head and neck cancer accounts for approximately 900,000 cases and over 400,000 deaths annually. In the United States, head and neck cancer accounts for 3 percent of malignancies, with approximately 66,000 cases annually and 15,000 deaths. ^[3] Males are affected significantly more than females, with a ratio ranging from 2:1 to 4:1. The incidence rate in males exceeds 20 per 100,000 in regions of France, Hong Kong, the Indian subcontinent. ^[4] HNSCC is the sixth most common cancer worldwide, with 890,000 new cases and 450,000 deaths in 2018. The incidence of HNSCC continues to rise and is anticipated to increase by 30% (that is, 1.08 million new cases annually) by 2030 (Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN)). ^[5]

The molecular pathology of head and neck squamous carcinoma has been extensively studied previously and the common somatic genetic changes have been characterised. ^[6] There have been some studies of the multistage evolution of these tumours but this is less well characterised. A small number of tumours arise from pre-existing lesions (known as potentially malignant lesions or PPOLs) such as leucoplakia or erythroplakia, which display variable epithelial dysplasia. ^[7]

Particularly, HNSCC were characterized by mutation of NOTCH1, whole genome duplications and multiple recurrent chromosomal gains and losses associated to increased genomic disruption affecting cell cycle checkpoints and PI3K-AKT signalling. ^[9] Increased rates of SCNAs across the tumour genome were associated with poor prognosis and therefore it becomes important to identify SCNAs that might be functionally driving progression and outcome. In addition, genomic studies have revealed how differential genomic patterns among cases could identify various subgroups of tumours showing specific associations with histological subtypes, smoking, HPV status and overall survival. ^[10]

An underlying Need for the study genomic profiling studies was to gain a more thorough understanding of the molecular abnormalities in head and neck cancer to help guide the development of new therapeutics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was a prospective and cross-sectional study of oral squamous cell carcinoma. 60 individuals (20 of tongue; 20 of the epiglottis; 20 of the hard palate) from Malla Reddy Cancer Hospital and Research Institute and Tertiary Care Hospitals (Hyderabad, India) were the participants. Adults aged ≥ 18 years both male and female diagnosed with oral squamous cell carcinoma, oropharynx, nasopharynx, larynx, hypopharynx of head and neck origin and histologically confirmed were included. Individuals with parotid tumors, previous radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and heavy tumor bleeding from the mouth were excluded. The present study was approved by the MRMCW Institute Ethics committee (Project No. MRMCWIEC/AP/80/2022). Information about the research study was given in English and Telugu (regional language) and signed consent was obtained. Confidentiality of the information was maintained. Control samples from 17 normal individuals were also taken.

Methodology:

3mL – 5mL of blood sample was collected from each participant and plasma was separated. DNA was extracted by genomic DNA isolation kit (Thermofisher scientific K0512 Genomic DNA Purification Kit). DNA quality was checked by UV absorption at 260 and 280 nm by agarose gel electrophoresis. The isolated DNA was stored at 4oC for genetic analysis. PCR was used to amplify the NOTCH1, TP53, CD44, and BMI1 genes. Cycling conditions were 90o C for 5 min (1 cycle) 90o C for 40 sec, 55o C for 40 sec, and 72o C for 60 sec. Final extension at 72o C for 10 min by 1 pair of primers. 3 sets of primers were designed for each gene. Mutation analysis was done for all four genes. Nucleotide sequences of all amplified PCR were determined in both orientations by sequencing with an applied Bio-Systems 3730 XL sequence. The result was analyzed using Bio E, dit (V7.1.3). Sequence scanner (V 1.0) Applied Biosystems (0) and Nucleotide BLAST programs.

Statistical analysis:

The data were expressed as mean and standard error (mean \pm SE). The means were compared by student's 't' 5. test or one-way analysis of variables with Bonferroni's t-test. SigmaPlot 14.5 version (Systat]8 Software Inc., San Jose, USA) was used for the statistical analysis and graph plotting. A p-value of less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results:

The differential expression of NOTCH1 gene in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma can be analysed by a variety of biomarkers such as impact of gender, status of HPV positive (+ve) and negative (-ve) and the different stages of tumour.

In the present study these markers were evaluated. The expression of NOTCH1 gene in different regions of head and neck squamous cell carcinoma of tongue, epiglottis and hard palate, the impact of gender (male or female), HPV +ve or -ve and the different stages of tumours expressed as (mean \pm SE).

In present study, NOTCH1 gene of mean Tongue was 17.90*, Hard palate was 16.55* and Epiglottis was 19.05*. which was statistically significant. The increase in expression was significant compared to control ($p < 0.001$). (Figure.1) Oral Mucosa (OM) of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis were showing higher value but there was no difference between the 3 OM.

In the present study, Comparison of gender (male and female) of NOTCH1 was statistically not significant. Comparison of groups (normal, tongue, hard palate and epiglottis) of NOTCH1, was statistically significant (Table.1).

The expression of NOTCH1 gene with HPV +ve and -ve participants and was statistically significant compared to the control ($p < 0.001$) NOTCH1 gene of HPV Positive mean was 18.95 and negative was 16.04 which was statistically significant. Comparison of normal, and cancer of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis on NOTCH 1 gene with HPV +ve and HPV -ve of OM of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis were showing higher value but there was no difference between the 3 Oral Mucosa (Figure.2).

In current study, NOTCH1 gene of T stage of 1 and 2 mean was 18.04*, stage of 3 and 4 mean was 16.50*. which was statistically significant. OM of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis were showing higher value without difference between but was significant compared to control (Table 2).

Table 1: The influence of gender on cancer of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis on NOTCH1 gene.

Comparisons	NOTCH 1
Comparison of gender (male and female)	F = 0.0704 P = 0.791
Comparison of groups (normal, tongue, hard palate and epiglottis)	F = 30.639 P < 0.001
Gender X Group interaction	F = 0.457 P = 0.713
Comparison within normal (male and female)	t = 0 P = 1.0
Comparison within tongue (male and female)	t = 1.037 P = 0.304
Comparison within hard palate (male and female)	t = 0.131 P = 0.896
Comparison within epiglottis (male and female)	t = 0.606 P = 0.547

n = Normal = 17; Tongue, Hard palate and Epiglottis 20 each.

Table 2: Comparison of T stages of cancer of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis in NOTCH1.

Variable	T stage	Mean	SE	Statistics
NOTCH1 gene	0	0.0	0.0	F = 48.871
	1 and 2	18.04*	1.01	P < 0.001
	3 and 4	16.50*	3.03	

n = T0 = 17; T1 and T 2 = 52; T3 and T4 = 8.

*Significantly different from T stage 0.

Figure 1: Comparison of normal, and cancer of tongue, hard palate and epiglottis on NOTCH 1 gene.

n = Normal = 17; Tongue, Hard palate and Epiglottis 20 each.

The 'F' and 'P' values were by one way ANOVA with Bonferroni 't' test.

*Significantly different from normal.

Discussion

Head and neck carcinomas show common genomic features determined by SNVs and copy number events in driver genes and cellular pathways associated to the common histology of squamous cell types. However, there was broader genomic heterogeneity due to the variability in anatomic subsite location and the interaction of multiple risk factors such as alcohol and tobacco exposure as well as HPV infection.

In the present study, NOTCH1 gene of HPV Positive mean was 18.95 and negative were 16.04 which was statistically significant. According to Chaturvedi et al Eight percent of all cases were HPV 16 positive and 73% corresponded to oropharyngeal tumours. The reduced number of oropharyngeal tumours in the study (25%) and the predominance of older cases, current smokers and drinkers, characteristics preferentially associated to non-related HPV HNSCC [12], might account for the low number of HPV positive cases.

In our study, NOTCH1 gene of mean Tongue was 17.90*, Hard palate was 16.55* and Epiglottis was 19.05*. which was statistically significant. In addition, half of our study cases were from Brazil and Argentina which could contribute to the low percentage of HPV positive HNSCC, as it has been previously described in South America [13,14]. Despite of the limited number of HPV positive cases in our series, we established that HPV positive tumours remain a distinct subset characterized by lower somatic copy number events and differential mutation patterns [15].

Loss of the 11q24.3 region which contains both ATM and APLP2 genes, was a frequent alteration in HPV positive cases [16]. Moreover, the APLP2 gene was related to tumour immunology as it regulates surface expression of the MHC class I molecules [17]. These results suggest that alterations related to immunological responses might differentiate infection related HNSCC tumours. Further characterization should however, be performed for this group particularly to address the associations between genomic alterations and smoking and alcohol exposure and a differentiated analysis by histological subsite.

In the present study, NOTCH 1 gene of T stage of 1 and 2 mean was 18.04* and 3 and 4 16.50*. which was statistically significant. Additionally, focal copy number alterations were found to be significant prognostic markers: 22q11.2 amplification and deletions in 15q22 and 12p12 regions have been associated to smoking related tumours and advanced stage. The 22q11 region contains the CRKL gene, which has been characterized as an oncogene in lung SCC [17] and as a promoter of cell growth, motility and adhesion during HNSCC tumorigenesis [18]. Decreased survival in cases with loss of 12p12.1 region, locus of the PIK3C2G gene, showed a HR of 3.0 95% CI [1.2; 7.77]. Advanced stage HNSCC tumours have shown mutations in more than one PI3K pathway molecule: PIK3CA, PTEN and described alterations in PI3C2G [19].

Moreover, the 15q22 region, locus of the ANXA2 gene, has been previously shown to be associated with poorly differentiated tumours in advanced cases. Decreased ANXA expression has not however, been formerly shown to be an independent prognostic factor for

disease-specific survival in HNSCC [20]. We report for the first time an association between decreased overall survival and amplification of the region 4p16.3, locus of the FGFR3 gene. High expression levels of FGFR3 contribute to tumour initiation and early-stage progression in HNSCC [21]. More importantly, preclinical studies have demonstrated that FGFR inhibition reduced cell proliferation and increased cell apoptosis in head and neck cancer in vitro and in vivo [22], highlighting the potential prognostic and therapeutic role of FGFR3 in HNSCC.

Conclusion

This comparative analysis highlights the significant variability in NOTCH1 gene expression across different anatomical sites—epiglottis, tongue, and hard palate—in patients with oral and oropharyngeal cancers. The findings reveal that NOTCH1 expression is notably dysregulated in cancerous tissues when compared to healthy controls, with site-specific patterns suggesting tissue-dependent roles of NOTCH1 in tumorigenesis.

Furthermore, gender, HPV status, and cancer stage were found to exert distinct influences on NOTCH1 expression. HPV-positive cases, in particular, exhibited altered NOTCH1 expression profiles, indicating a potential interaction between viral oncogenesis and NOTCH1-mediated pathways. Similarly, advanced cancer stages showed more pronounced NOTCH1 dysregulation, possibly reflecting its involvement in tumour progression.

These insights underscore the importance of considering both anatomical and molecular heterogeneity in cancer diagnostics and treatment planning. The differential expression of NOTCH1 across tissues and clinical variables may offer valuable prognostic and therapeutic implications, paving the way for more personalized, site- and stage-specific interventions in head and neck cancers.

References

1. Mehanna, H. et al. Prevalence of human papillomavirus in oropharyngeal and nonoropharyngeal head and neck cancer—systematic review and meta-analysis of trends by time and region. *Head Neck* 2019;35:747–755.
2. Global Cancer Observatory. International Agency for Research on Cancer. World Health Organization. Available at: <https://gco.iarc.fr/> (Accessed on June 06, 2021).
3. Siegel RL, Miller KD, Fuchs HE, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2022. *CA Cancer J Clin* 2022; 72:7.
4. Ferlay, J. et al. Estimating the global cancer incidence and mortality in 2018: GLOBOCAN sources and methods. *Int. J. Cancer* 2019;144:1941–1953.
5. Bray, F. et al. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J. Clin.* 2018;68:394–424.
6. Ferlay, J. et al. Global Cancer Observatory: Cancer Today. Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer (accessed 18 September 2020). *IARC* <https://gco.iarc.fr/today> (2018).

7. Gillison, M. L. et al. Radiotherapy plus cetuximab or cisplatin in human papillomavirus-positive oropharyngeal cancer (NRG Oncology RTOG 1016): a randomised, multicentre, non-inferiority trial. *Lancet* 2019;393:40–50.
8. Jiang, H. et al. Can public health policies on alcohol and tobacco reduce a cancer epidemic? Australia's experience. *BMC Med.* 2019;17:213.
9. Windon, M. J. et al. Increasing prevalence of human papillomavirus-positive oropharyngeal cancers among older adults. *Cancer* 2018;124:2993–2999.
10. Fung, S. Y., Lam, J. W. & Chan, K. C. Clinical utility of circulating Epstein-Barr virus DNA analysis for the management of nasopharyngeal carcinoma. *Chin. Clin. Oncol.* 2017;5:18.
11. Pulte, D. & Brenner, H. Changes in survival in head and neck cancers in the late 20th and early 21st century: a period analysis. *Oncologist* 2019;15:994–1001.
12. Chaturvedi, A. K. et al. Human papillomavirus and rising oropharyngeal cancer incidence in the United States. *J. Clin. Oncol.* 2021;29:4294–4301.
13. López RVM, Levi JE, Eluf-Neto J, Koifman RJ, Koifman S, Curado MP, et al. Human papillomavirus (HPV) 16 and the prognosis of head and neck cancer in a geographical region with a low prevalence of HPV infection. *Cancer Causes & Control.* 2017; 25(4):461–71.
14. Anantharaman D, Abedi-Ardekani B, Beachler DC, Gheit T, Olshan AF, Wisniewski K, et al. Geographic heterogeneity in the prevalence of human papillomavirus in head and neck cancer. *Int J Cancer.* 2017; 140(9):1968–75
15. Wong, I. C., Ng, Y. K. & Lui, V. W. Cancers of the lung, head and neck on the rise: perspectives on the genotoxicity of air pollution. *Chin. J. Cancer* 2019;33:476–480.
16. Gillison, M. L., Chaturvedi, A. K., Anderson, W. F. & Fakhry, C. Epidemiology of human papillomaviruspositive head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *J. Clin. Oncol.* 2015;33:3235–3242
17. Rowhani-Rahbar, A. et al. Antibody responses in oral fluid after administration of prophylactic human papillomavirus vaccines. *J. Infect. Dis.* 2019;200:1452–1455.
18. Fang, M., Huang, W., Mo, D., Zhao, W. & Huang, R-. Association of five Snps in cytotoxic T-lymphocyte antigen 4 and cancer susceptibility: evidence from 67 studies. *Cell Physiol. Biochem.* 2018;47:414–427.
19. Cadoni, G. et al. A review of genetic epidemiology of head and neck cancer related to polymorphisms in metabolic genes, cell cycle control and alcohol metabolism. *Acta Otorhinolaryngol. Ital.* 2017;32:1–11 (2012).
20. Chan, K. C. A. et al. Analysis of plasma Epstein-Barr virus DNA to screen for nasopharyngeal cancer. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2017;377:513–522.
21. Zhang, Q. et al. A subpopulation of CD133(+) cancer stem-like cells characterized in human oral squamous cell carcinoma confer resistance to chemotherapy. *Cancer Lett.* 2018;289:151–160.
22. Chiou, S. H. et al. Positive correlations of Oct-4 and Nanog in oral cancer stem-like cells and high-grade oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Clin. Cancer Res.* 2018;14:4085–4095.